

Variability of rice koji for enzyme activities using *Basidiomycetes*

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Current mushroom research has concentrated more on nutritional and medicinal aspects. Mushrooms belong to a class of fungi called *Basidiomycetes*, which are a source of important enzymes used in making food and medicine. A liquid culture of mycelium and carpophore is commonly used to extract and refine these enzymes. This method, however, is time- and labor-consuming and costly.

Cereals can also be used as a solid substrate to culture *Basidiomycetes*. Rice *koji*, a product made from rice, can be used as a culture medium to produce *Aspergillus oryzae*, a source of enzymes such as alpha-, beta-, and glucoamylase and protease. β -amylase is used to make yoghurt, vinegar, and alcohol, whereas protease can be used to produce soy sauce and other food ingredients.

We studied the possibility of using rice koji media for mushroom culture and examined the variability of enzyme activities on these media. The experiment, replicated six times, was carried out at the Laboratory of Rice Processing, NHAES, in 1998.

We used rice koji from five cultivars with different quality characteristics (Dongjinbyeo, Hyangnambyeo, Yangjobyeo, Heugnambyeo, and Sinseonchalbyeo) and

four *Basidiomycetes* (*Pleurotus ostreatus*, *Lentineus edodes*, *Hericium erinaceus*, and *Ganoderma lucidum*). The degree of mycelial growth of the *Basidiomycetes* on rice koji was scored visually 20 d after culture, and enzyme activities of protease and β -amylase were measured by standard procedures. Statistical analysis was done using Duncan's multiple range test (DMRT).

Results showed that mycelial growth was better in *P. ostreatus* and *G. lucidum* than in the other two *Basidiomycetes*. Among the rice koji cultivars, poor mycelial growth was observed in Sinseonchalbyeo, whereas active growth was noted in the others (Table 1). This is because Sinseonchalbyeo is a waxy (glutinous) variety. Adding water makes its granules sticky, thus retarding mycelial growth of *Basidiomycetes*.

Among the *Basidiomycetes*, the highest β -amylase activity was observed in *G. lucidum* (450–538 units, Table 2), whereas the highest protease activity was seen in *P. ostreatus* (17.9–33.1). Among the cultivars tested as culture media, Heugnambyeo had the highest β -amylase and protease activities. These results indicate that rice *koji* of Heugnambyeo with *G. lucidum* and *P. ostreatus* can be used as a good source of β -amylase and protease, respectively. It can also be used as a substitute for liquid culture in extracting enzymes for food. Because Heugnambyeo has high micronutrients, correlation between micronutrients and enzymes could be further examined.

Table 1. Mycelial growth of *Basidiomycetes* on rice koji media, Korea, 1998.^a

Variety	<i>Pleurotus ostreatus</i>	<i>Lentineus edodes</i>	<i>Hericium erinaceus</i>	<i>Ganoderma lucidum</i>
Dongjinbyeo	+++	++	++	+++
Hyangnambyeo	+++	++	++	+++
Yangjobyeo	+++	++	++	+++
Heugnambyeo	+++	++	++	+++
Sinseonchalbyeo	+++	+	++	+++

^a++ = bad, +++ = good.

Table 2. β -amylase and protease activities^a in rice koji using *Basidiomycetes*, Korea, 1998.

Variety	β -amylase (units)				Protease (units)			
	<i>Pleurotus ostreatus</i>	<i>Lentineus edodes</i>	<i>Hericium erinaceus</i>	<i>Ganoderma lucidum</i>	<i>Pleurotus ostreatus</i>	<i>Lentineus edodes</i>	<i>Hericium erinaceus</i>	<i>Ganoderma lucidum</i>
Dongjinbyeo	137.3 e	393.2 c	87.7 c	466.0 d	17.9 c	11.3 a	15.9 c	11.2 c
Hyangnambyeo	208.6 b	401.0 b	111.8 b	523.3 b	19.9 c	9.9 b	16.3 c	16.6 a
Yangjobyeo	155.7 d	309.2 d	68.5 d	450.3 e	21.9 c	7.8 c	22.1 b	16.6 a
Heugnambyeo	170.7 c	518.3 a	64.1 d	538.2 a	33.1 a	7.8 c	25.8 a	12.1 b
Sinseonchalbyeo	259.0 a	402.5 b	117.3 a	497.8 c	27.9 b	11.4 a	22.3 b	11.5 c

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.